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Sexually dimorphic morphological traits in melon fruit fly, *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett) is well recognized pest fruit fly predominantly spread in Indian subcontinent. Its two sexes can be easily identified by the presence of pointed ovipositor at the posterior abdominal tip of female and a rounded abdominal end in male. Besides this, we have identified the presence of pecten hairs on the dorsal surface of abdomen and a distinct posterior depression in the wings restricted in males only. Wings in the males also show bushy appearance of microtrichia at post anal lobe which is totally lacking in females. The number of pecten hairs showed normal distribution pattern on right and left halves of the abdomen. An analysis pertaining to the distribution of pecten hairs on both sides of abdomen revealed non-significant difference between the mean numbers of hairs of the two sides.

Keywords: Cucurbitaceae; Pecten hairs; Microtrichia; Oviscape; Aculeus; Melon fruit fly.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sexual dimorphism refers to contrasting morphological features between male and female of a species. Dioecious insects show distinct sexually dimorphic characters [1]. In most of the cases, females are generally the larger sex which is due to selective pressure of fecundity and a positive correlation between female body size and fecundity. This aspect has already been reported in many insect species Shine [2-4].

Bactrocera cucurbitae is melon fruit fly and is a highly destructive pest species of fruits and vegetables of family Cucurbitaceae. This insect pest belongs to family Tephritidae of order Diptera. Its damaging nature has substantially been investigated by a number of entomologists [5-7]. Asymmetrical distribution of its members due to colour preference matching with the host plants has been reported in *B. cucurbitae* [8]. Substantial amount of study has been done on the control of this insect pest by using sterile insect technique (SIT) under which mass reared sterile males are released in the field to compete with non-sterile males for mating purpose [5]. This insect pest can be easily identified for its sex by simple observation as its female possesses pointed ovipositor at the posterior tip of its abdomen which lacks in male [5].

While observing the morphological features of *B. cucurbitae*, we have been able to observe some more sexually dimorphic features in the two sexes which have not been reported at all by earlier researchers. In this paper, we are reporting some salient characteristics of such unnoticed dimorphic features in this pest species.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted on the laboratory reared flies of *B. cucurbitae* maintained for several generations. Flies were maintained in laboratory at $26\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature, $65\pm 5\%$ relative humidity and 12:12 light and dark cycle. Sexually mature flies of 8-10 days age were carefully used for their morphological examination. 100 male and 100 female flies were observed for their morphological features like wings, pecten hairs of male and ovipositor of females, which were considered for sexual differences between the two sexes. Pecten hairs, found on the dorsal side of abdomen of male flies were identified for the first time and were distributed on either side from the median dorsal position. By using stereo-binocular, the number of pecten hairs were counted on both side of male flies ($N=100$). The data obtained with respect to pecten hairs of right and left sides were analyzed by unpaired t-test to see whether the mean number of hairs of the two sides differ significantly.

3. RESULTS

Morphologically, the two sexes of *B. cucurbitae* look different from each other on the basis of variation of their posterior abdominal structure. Figure 1 depicts microphotograph of female and male individuals of this fly.

Figure 1. *Bactrocera cucurbitae*, A: Female, B: Male.

Its female possesses a protruding ovipositor (Figure 2). In normal condition ovipositor is a smaller structure extending at the tip of posterior abdominal segment but at the time of egg laying, it gets elongated to position the egg in the fleshy food material. Ovipositor sheath, a segment between oviscape and aculeus regulates the size of the ovipositor.

Figure 3 shows microphotographs of wings of females and males of *B. cucurbitae*. A distinct depression exists at the lower edge of male wing. Bushy microtrichia is found only in male wing and that can be a convincing feature to identify the two sexes. In females, the wing outline is regular with only slight depression at certain position, but in males, there is great depression in wing outline in posterior region near “cell bcu” position which creates a lobe in wing of males. In males, at cell bcu extension, there is formation of bushy appearance of microtrichia. Sketch diagram of male wing showing different morphological features is shown in Figure 4.

When the abdominal portion is observed in its ventral view, marked differences in the two sexes can also be seen. In female fly, four abdominal rectangular brownish-black patches are present whereas, in male counterpart, only three round brownish patches are seen (Figure 5).

Fly abdominal region (dorsal view)

Figure 2. Sketch showing different segments of female ovipositor.

Figure 3. Stereo-binocular microphotograph of wing of both sexes. A: Female, B: Male.

Figure 4. Sketch diagram of male wing showing different morphological features.

Figure 5. Stereo binocular micrograph of ventral view of abdominal region A: Female B: Male.

Figure 6. Pecten hairs in male, A. sketch diagram, B. stereo binocular image.

Figure 7. Normal distribution pattern of pecten hair number in *Bactrocera cucurbitae*.

Pecten hairs are found only in male and such structures can be spotted on the dorsal surface of mid abdomen (Figure 6). Figure 7 depicts normal distribution pattern of pecten hairs number in the right and left side of abdomen. A statistical analysis to know whether significant difference exist between the mean number of hairs on the two side revealed non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

4. DISCUSSION

Sexual dimorphism is the morphological variation between male and female individuals of a species. Insects are mainly sexually dimorphic and the cause of distinct differences in the two sexes of a number of species is credited to sexual selection. In a gross morphology of male and female, some of the features are so obvious that simple observation of the individual enables the viewer to identify its sex. Whereas, there are certain features which do need microscopic observations for enough clarity and such features may be associated with long course of sexual selection. Sexual size dimorphism (SSD) which is inequality in size occurs in most of the insects and animals with female generally larger in size [9, 10]. In most of the invertebrates and cold blooded animals, females are the larger sex which may be linked to the high fecundity. Male related sexual size dimorphism is dominant in avian and mammals system for attracting females for mating purposes [11]. Formation of certain appendages or structures in one sex during the course of time may have certain advantages in sexual preferences or mating purpose and mimicry [12]. Female prefers to mate with highly ornamented males [11].

One of the dipterans insects group, i.e., *Drosophila* is represented by hundreds of species. Identification of the members of different species of this genus can be achieved by observing the colour and shape of their posterior abdominal segments. However, males possess sex comb in the tarsal segment/s of first pair of thoracic legs. The structure and pattern of sex comb is species specific and help biologists to identify different species of *Drosophila*. Only through sex comb number and pattern, hundreds of its species have been identified and has helped the *Drosophila* taxonomists to decide its sibling species or to delineate into species groups and subgroups. Ng and Kopp [13] stated that *D. melanogaster* males make use of their sex combs in grasping the female's abdomen and genitalia and to spread their wings at the time of copulation. They observed that the loss of the sex comb strongly reduces the ability of males to copulate with females.

In *B. cucurbitae*, the female fly possesses pointed ovipositor at the posterior end of its abdomen and the male one has rounded abdominal end. The female ovipositor is long telescopic type and is of retractile in nature. It can be sectioned in three segments i.e. oviscape, eversible ovipositor sheath and aculeus [14]. The ovipositor sheath muscles can lead to the extension of ovipositor up to the length of abdomen and shows movement in any direction, when not in use, the ovipositor is retracted to general length. The gross structure is enough to identify the two sexes at a glance. However, males possess some intricate features which can be of evolutionary significance to this species. Pectens are hair like, dark coloured structures present on dorsal surface of third abdominal lining on either side of body i.e. on left and right body halves in horizontal line in monopectinate order. These pecten hairs are found only in males and it can be one of the identifying features for males. Pecten hair number is found to vary from 10 to 21. The analysis of 100 males for their pecten number on both sides of abdomen revealed that there is normal distribution pattern of these hairs. The results of this observation thus clearly indicate that this meristic trait shows continuous inheritance pattern and is therefore a polygenic character.

In ventral abdominal region of both sexes, there are dark spots in median position. These spots starting from posterior most region decrease in size with each consecutive segment. In male, there are in total, three spots starting from just above the anal region, but in females, there are four such spots starting above the ovipositor. Variation in shape of these spots of the two sexes can be observed. In *B. cucurbitae*, specific function of pecten hairs is not known but possibly it is involved in sound production in males. Similarly occurrence of regular wing outline in females and incised wing in males may also have involvement in sound

production or mating preference. This study would now stimulate the biologists working in this field to consider the said traits in other species of this genus. The careful observation of these sexually dimorphic traits may help to identify the different taxonomic groups of this genus.

Author Contributions: SS and NY are rearing different strains of *Bactrocera cucurbitae* flies in the laboratory conditions. Both observed the sexually dimorphic traits and analyzed data. AKS helped in writing the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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